

Synodal Reality through Small Christian Communities

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Abstract

The Second Vatican Council threw open the doors of the Church by inviting the People of God to realize and actualise their baptismal vocation as priests, prophets and kings. The Church began a subtle transition from a hierarchical to a participative Church. Notwithstanding the vision of Vatican II, a Participatory Church was not actualised in subsequent years. Fifty years thereafter, Pope Francis now invites the Church to move beyond opening its doors by walking towards the populace to discover the Church's true purpose and identity. He exhorts the Church to pay attention to the peripheries; he envisions a Synodal Church that strives for participation, communion, and mission. Small Christian Communities are instrumental in actualizing this vision by involving the peripheries. It brings to mind bygone days when the Church originated in people's homes, thus emphasizing the necessity to be a New Church that journeys together.

Introduction

The rise and remarkable spread of the Small Christian Communities (SCCs) are undoubtedly one of the most striking signs of the Church's present-day vitality and future growth. Through the SCCs, the Church has rediscovered such an ideal as well as its real identity and is accordingly recreating itself, and precisely that is what Synod on Synodality envisions: Participation, Communion, and Mission. In them, it is no more a congregation of anonymous persons who come together only to worship their God without really coming to know, care for and share with one another. The SCCs have also admirably succeeded in concretizing the new vision of the Church as the people of God as proposed by

Vat II. In *Christifideles Laici* we read: The ecclesiology of communion is a central and fundamental concept in the Conciliar documents. Communion (*Koinonia*) finding its source in Sacred Scripture, was a concept held in great honor in the early Church and in the Oriental Churches, and this teaching endures to the present day. In this article, I will be explaining the significant role Small Christian Communities play to become a participatory church.

Spirituality and the Significance of SCCs

Communion is manifested when two or three people are gathered in Christ's name. It is manifested when the Word of God is proclaimed, listened to, and lived in a community. It is manifested when one shares the joys and sufferings of one's neighbors. And this kind of communion takes place better in small groups and in the full sense in Small Christian Communities. At times, in urban areas, it becomes difficult for larger groups to experience communion. Family, though the basic unit of the Church and society, does not adopt a public value system and can remain internally oriented. In the present-day context of nuclear families, it is all the more difficult to express a value system. The membership in the family is by birth, while in an ecclesial community, it is a matter of Christian commitment which comprises a mission. The people of a parish scattered in different sections of the parish cannot be formed into communion through a liturgical service alone. The liturgy ought to be an expression of their living together in communion all the days of the week. They need to understand that growing together in unity and fraternal love demands that people meet regularly in smaller groups in which close interaction and witnessing together are possible. SCCs make this journey to communion a reality of a participatory Church.

Word of God

This is the focal point of the spirituality of SCCs. One of the very important achievements of the formation of SCCs is that even ordinary people have begun to read the Holy Scripture in their community gatherings. In fact, there is a paradigm shift as regards the approach to the Scripture. Before Second Vatican Council the Sacred Scripture was treated almost like some secret writing that should be used only by experts in theology and in official preaching. In the SCCs the people, who come as an ecclesial community read the Bible, meditate over it, and share their own reflections. The Word of God becomes no more a private transaction between God and some selected individuals, but the faith story of a community of believers. Hence, the Bible belongs to the people of God as a community. The Word of God is familiarized in the SCCs through the

commonly used seven steps method, called ‘Gospel Sharing’. In short, the use of Scripture in the SCCs directs and shapes the lives of people. The Word of God becomes the touchstone of their day-to-day life.

New Approach to Eucharist

The Word of God leads the people to the Eucharist. It becomes the center of ecclesial spirituality. It is the greatest symbol of covenant and communion. It becomes an occasion to proclaim the passion, death, and resurrection of Jesus Christ. Although the Eucharist is not celebrated in the SCCs generally, it is through the SCCs that the liturgical celebrations are made lively on Sundays. For the SCCs are directly involved in giving introduction, scripture reading, the prayer of the faithful, community singing, etc. In short, the communitarian aspect of the Eucharist is well reflected in the celebration of Sunday liturgy. Through the active participation in the liturgy, they slowly identify with the life of Jesus.

Personal and Communitarian Commitment

The spirituality of SCCs is personal and communitarian (Rev 3:20-21). God calls everyone personally. The response to the personal call implies the building up of a community. The dynamic relation between person and community in human life is relevant also in the case of the Christian life. The dynamic and intimate relationship between a person and the community is well expressed in the exhortation of St. Paul to the Corinthian community. According to him the particular manifestation of the Spirit granted to each one is to be used for the benefit of others (1 Cor 12:4-11). The personal and communitarian response becomes meaningful when it helps one to follow Jesus Christ.

New Experience in Following Jesus Christ

One of the important expressions of the spirituality of SCCs is the determination of its members to follow Jesus Christ. To follow Jesus Christ in the biblical point of view signifies a response to his call. For example, Jesus Christ calls his disciples to follow Him (Mk 1:16-20). In the SCCs the people see the invisible presence of God in the Paschal mystery of Jesus Christ. They experience a personal God in Jesus Christ who not only speaks to them but also seeks them out. More than the parish centered Christianity the SCCs try to realize the personal and communitarian commitment in following Jesus Christ. Behind this commitment, we see the concern and compassion of each individual for the other. That indeed is a Mission given to each of us, to go beyond oneself in love

and service of one's neighbor.

To Love One's Neighbour

The commitment to follow Jesus Christ leads the members of SCCs to express their concern and commitment to their neighbors. The members are challenged to love not imaginary neighbours but the neighbours who live close to them, the neighbours whose children are to be sent to school, who are not able to build a house for their family, who have no means to meet the hospital expenses, who does not have a vision about his family. Loving one's neighbours is loving God himself. "Anyone who says, I love God and hates his brother is a liar, since whoever does not love the brother whom he sees cannot love God whom he has not seen" (1Jn 4:20). In the concrete situation of the SCC gatherings the members encounter the poor and needy.

Living in the Cultural Situation

Solidarity with the poor is closely connected with the spirituality of the SCCs. A follower of Jesus Christ cannot but be in solidarity with the poor. Solidarity with the poor has to take a concrete form. It has to be realized at the grassroots level in its cultural situation. As John Paul II notes, the Church lives and fulfills its Mission in the actual circumstances of time and place. Explaining the challenges of inculturation the Pope says that "culture is the vital space within which the human person comes face to face with the Gospel. Just as a culture is the result of the life and activity of a human group, so the persons belonging to that group are shaped to a large extent by the culture in which they live".

Conclusion

The renowned theologian Karl Rahner emphatically predicted the Church of the future will be one built from below by basic communities as a result of free initiative and association. Whether one wants it or not, the future of the Church will belong to the SCCs. SCC makes the Synodal dream of Pope Francis a reality; where Participation, Communion, and Mission become the central focus. The challenges and difficulties that the SCCs encounter are the transitory obstacles that will surely be overcome in the near future. Challenges are the part and parcel of human life, without which there will not be any dynamism in our life. By confronting the problems, the SCCs are more vivified to become the leaven and salt of the Church so as to transform it to be a participatory Church and a powerful instrument of Kingdom of God. Let us face the challenges and establish a new world filled with the Kingdom values. A community will be a

happy place if we have one goal. This does not mean that all will do the same work. All of us are called to commit ourselves to the Kingdom of God. And this commitment should become the uniting force among all members. It is so unfortunate that often one sees a lot of jealousy and a lack of mutual support and encouragement in the communities. If everyone sees his or her work as a contribution towards a common goal of the community, all will be led to mutual appreciation, support, and encouragement. If we have the attitude that another's success is my success; another's failure is my failure, I think we will make a true religious community. One cannot work for the kingdom of God if one does not live by the values of the kingdom: respect for the freedom of others, loving others, serving others, admiring the dignity of others, etc.

This analysis too shows me that “I am the church and we are the church” and therefore, all must work to bring the Kingdom values on this earth. I have realized that my local church is a sacrament of communion through the realization of “I am the church” and all of us must work to build the church very strongly with deep-rooted foundations. Pope Francis’ Servant model church can be actualized through the SCCs. The thrust of this article was, ‘The Wake Up Call for the Church’, inspired by Pope Francis who writes in *Evangelii Gaudium* 49, “I prefer a Church which is bruised, hurting and dirty because it has been out on the streets, rather than a Church which is unhealthy from being confined and from clinging to its own security. If something should rightly disturb us and trouble our consciences, it is the fact that so many of our brothers and sisters are living without the strength, light and consolation born of friendship with Jesus Christ, without a community of faith to support them, without meaning and a goal in life.” SCCs will make this vision come true at grass root level.

Despite the privileged, clerical, institutional approach to spirituality that exists in the church, new evangelical missions are being propagated through recent papal declarations. The new missionary activities encouraged by the Vatican Council II are not executed for the exclusive purpose of conversion or expanding the Church but for giving to people Jesus Christ. Thus, new missionary activity, though ecclesiastically organized in some way, should be no more Church-centered but Gospel-centered and community-centered. It is a proclamation and an invitation to live the Gospel as a community that becomes the Church. Through the new missionary activities, conversion can take place, and churches can grow, but the main focus of evangelization is enabling an encounter of the Christian community with the Gospel of Jesus Christ. And within this Christian community, it is imperative to seek the lost sheep, the

neglected sect of the society- the poorest of the poor who, deprived at many levels, thirst for Christ.

References

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